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Systematic discovery of cell and immune function in IBD: the exhaustion program.

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The influence of the effectors and receptors of the exhaustion program to cell and molecular biology of IBD in humans included the function of *BATF2*.

Citations

1. Guler, R., Mpotje, T., Ozturk, M., Nono, J.K., Parihar, S.P., Chia, J.E., Aziz, N.A., Hlaka, L., Kumar, S., Roy, S. and Penn-Nicholson, A., 2019. Batf2 differentially regulates tissue immunopathology in Type 1 and Type 2 diseases. *Mucosal immunology*, 12(2), pp.390-402.